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15. Two New Inscriptions from Agrahāra Bāchahaḷli
S. Nagarajappa 95
16. A Newly Discovered Paramāra Inscription of
Ajayavarma from Sohāgpūr - A Brief Note
Rajesh Mehar and S. Krishnamurthy 103
17. Irukkanturai Inscriptions and their significance - A Study
C. Shanthalingam 113
18. Gōrakpur Grant of the Gāhaḍavāla king Gōvindachandra, Saṁvat 1176
D.P. Dubey 118

A Newly Discovered Paramāra Inscription of Ajayavarma from Sohāgpūr - A Brief Note

Rajesh Mehar and S. Krishnamurthy

The inscription, edited below for the first time with the kind permission of the Director (Epigraphy), Archaeological Survey of India, Mysuru, was discovered by the first author during the course of archaeological exploration in and around Sohāgpūr in Hoshangabad district of Madhya Pradesh.¹ It was brought to the notice of the Epigraphy Branch in February 2016 by Dr. Sachin Kumar Tiwari, Deputy Superintending Archaeologist, Excavation Branch, Archaeological Survey of India, Nagpur and is copied by the second author during epigraphical survey of that region. The stone bearing the inscription was in fact found in the year 2011 from an agricultural field belonging to Sri Prabadh Chand Tiwari, an Advocate by profession and is now preserved in his house at Sohāgpūr.

Description of the site

Sohāgpūr (Lat. 22° 42' 04.1" N; Long. 78° 11' 51.8" E), the tahsil headquarters is situated in Hoshangabad district of Madhya Pradesh, on the bank of Palakmatī river, a tributary of Narmadā. It lies at a distance of 51 km from Hoshangabad and 125 km from Bhopal. According to popular belief the old name of Sohāgpūr was Sonitāpūr (city of blood) and was the capital city of the demon king Bāṇāsura, the commander of Mahādēva.² It was also assumed by many historians that the Paramāra king Muñja transferred his capital from Ujjain³ to this place, then known as Sonitāpūr.

The antiquity of Sohāgpūr is attested by the existence of an archaeological mound on the north-western part of the town. Remains of pottery and other archaeological remains can be found from all over the site. Unfortunately the mound lost its original character and is now flattened for agricultural purpose. Many sculptural and architectural remains affiliated to both Jaina and Brahmanical faiths, unearthed from time to time from different areas of the town, bespeaks of the rich cultural heritage of the place. Many of them can be seen placed near the modern temples or kept inside and worshipped. Still more can be found lying below the trees and some of the best architectural and sculptural specimens are preserved in the office of the Tahsildar in the town and in the archaeological museum at Hoshangabad. The agricultural field in which the present inscription is found was also part of an archaeological mound, now very much disturbed and has also yielded a decapitated image of a Jaina tīrthankara which could be contextually related to the inscription.

The inscription

The present inscription, dated Samvat 1244 (1186 A.D.), is one of the largest and well preserved of the stone inscriptions so far discovered belonging to the Paramāras of Mālwā. The importance of the inscription is that it gives for the first time a sheet anchor to date Ajayavarma, a successor of Yaśōvarman and its Jaina affiliation, which is a rarity among the inscriptions of Paramāra period.

The inscription is engraved on a well dressed slab of sandstone measuring 123 cm in length, 55 (minimum) to 66 cm (maximum) in breadth and 9 cm in thickness. It consists of 56 lines of writing, engraved systematically in straight lines with beautiful calligraphy, in Nāgarī characters and Sanskrit language. Its style indicates the exceptional skill of the engraver and the high proficiency of the composer. The inscriptions of Paramāra dynasty are well known for its literary value and the present inscription makes an invaluable addition to the epigraphical corpus having literary merit in its composition.

The inscription opens with the auspicious word *siddham*, followed by the phrase *ōm namaḥ sarvvajñāya* and invocatory verses addressed to Śāntijinēśvara. The genealogy of the Paramāra dynasty in the present inscription starts with Sīyaka (c. 945-73 A.D.). He was the son and successor of Vairisimha and can be regarded as the real founder of the Paramāra kingdom in Mālwā region. From his Harsōla copper plate⁴ dated Vikrama samvat 1005, it is known that he was a semi-independent ruler and was a feudatory of Rāshtrakūṭa king Akālarsha Kṛishṇa III (939-67 A.D.) bearing the titles *mahārājādhirāja* and *mahāmaṇḍalika-chūḍāmaṇi* at the time of issue of that grant. From the Udaipur *prasasti* we learnt that Sīyaka alias Harshadēva finally succeeded in attaining an independent status to the Paramāra kingdom by defeating the Rāshtrakūṭa king Kottiga at about 972 A.D.⁵

Sīyaka was succeeded by his son Utpalarāja (c. 973-95 A.D.). He is identified by scholars as the same as Vākpatirāja *alias* Muñja supported by inscriptional and contemporary literary evidences.⁶ Then this inscription refers to the rule of members of Paramāra family over Mālwā region and gives the name of rulers successively as Sindhurāja (*circa* 995-1000 A.D.), Bhōjadēva (*circa* 1000-1055 A.D.), Udayāditya (*circa* 1070-1093 A.D.), Naravarma (*circa* 1093-1134 A.D.), Yaśōvarma (*circa* 1134-1142 A.D.) and Ajayavarma in lines 39-40.

The purport of the inscription seems to record the renovation of certain Udadbhukta-*maṭha* (line 47) and construction and installation of the image of a Jaina deity probably, Śāntijinēśvara to the eastern side of the said *maṭha* (lines 48-49). It also refers to the installation of the images of the deities Ambikādēvī and Mañibhadra in the *dēvakulika* at Narmadāpurī (lines 49-51). The inscription refers to itself as *praśasti* and certain Maddala is mentioned as its composer.

Identification of Ajayavarma of this record

After Yaśōvarman, there are differences in the genealogy of the Paramāras given in the inscriptions, due to the degeneration of political affairs of Mālwa. It is known that during his reign, major portion of Mālwa was lost to the Chalukyas of Gujarat. The Ujjain inscription of Jayasīṃha Siddharāja,⁷ dated Vikrama samvat 1195 (1138 A.D.), reveals that Yaśōvarman faced defeat at his hands and some parts of the Mālwa became a province of Chalukyas. An undated inscription from Vardhamānapura⁸ shows that Yaśōvarman was succeeded by his eldest son Jayavarman. His reign witnessed the onslaughts of Jagadēkamalla (1139-49 A.D.) the Chālukya ruler of Kalyāṇa⁹ and his subordinate Hoysala chief Vishṇuvardhana (1128-42 A.D.).¹⁰ After Jayavarman I, certain Ballāḷa, perhaps a Hoysala chief ruled over Mālwa region.¹¹ Thus after the death of Jayavarman, the Paramāra rule over Mālwa came to an end. Perhaps, the three brothers of Jayavarman - Ajayavarma, Lakshmīvarman and Trailōkyavarman ruled simultaneously in south-eastern borders of Mālwa i.e. around Bhōpāl, Vidisha and Hōshangābād districts of Madhya Pradesh. So far no inscription of Ajayavarman was found and nothing is known regarding his rule. Lakshmīvarman, seems to have ascended the throne by 1143 A.D. as known through his earliest dated inscription and ruled the eastern part of the Paramāra kingdom.¹² His brother, Trilōkyavarman seems to have ruled around Vidisha and Nimar districts, as known through his undated inscription.¹³ However, both these rulers did not use the customary title of Paramāras i.e. *paramabhṭāraka-mahārājādhirāja-paramēśvara* and styled themselves only as *mahākumāra*, which shows their subdued power. It is interesting to note that the name Ajayavarman do not figure in their inscriptions and that of their successors and mentions only Jayavarman. There are also inscriptions¹⁴ which mention Lakshmīvarman and Trailōkyavarman as immediate successor of Yaśōvarman and omit Jayavarman's name as well.

Ajayavarman figures as a successor of Yaśōvarman and father of Vindhyavarman, in Piplianagar grant of Arjunavarman, dated 1210 A.D.¹⁵ and two more inscriptions

of the same king dated 1213 and 1215 A.D.¹⁶ and in the Māndhātā plates of his successors Dēvapāla, dated 1225 AD.¹⁷ and Jayavarman II, dated 1260 A.D.¹⁸ There are two contradictory views regarding the identification of Ajayavarman. Pratipal Bhatia regards him as one of the four sons of Yaśōvarman, the other three being - Jayavarman, Lakshmīvarman and Trailōkyavarman, all of whom figure in their respective inscriptions D.C. Ganguly views that both Jayavarman and Ajayavarman are one and the same person perhaps Ajayavarman, tried to occupy the throne of Māl̥wā, after the death of his elder brother, but his attempts proved futile and he remained dormant. However so far nothing is known regarding his rule or exact reign period due to lack of any inscriptional evidences. Thus this inscription under study, dated Saṁvat 1244 (1186 A.D.) can be regarded as the first record giving firm anchor to date the period of Ajayavarma. As his name is not prefixed with the customary title of the Paramāra kings i.e. *paramabhaṭṭāraka-mahārājādhirāja-paramēśvara*, it is difficult to suggest whether he exercised his power as a ruler. Perhaps in 1186 A.D., Ajayavarman commissioned this inscription, under the rule of his son and successor Vindhyavarman, who by then has achieved independent status to Paramāras and recovered greater part of Māl̥wā region. This fact finds mention in the commentary on *Vṛittaratnākara* composed by Sulhaṇa, a court poet of Vindhyavarman, and can be dated to 1190 A.D. and in the inscriptions of his successor Arjunavarman.²⁰

Place names mentioned in the inscription

Rēvāpura (line 18) - It could be identified as the modern place Rēwabānkhēḍi, situated on the bank of the river Naramda (*Rēwa*), about 18 kms north of Sohāgpūr.

Mālwa (lines 34 and 40) - Māl̥wā, comprised of western districts of Madhya Pradesh and parts of south-eastern Rajasthan.

Nīlagiri (line 34) - It is also referred to in an inscription of *mahākumāra* Hariśchandra, father of Udayavarman (the Piplianagar Copper Plate inscription dated Vikrama 1235 and 1236).²¹ D.C. Ganguly identified the place Nīlagiri-maṇḍala as the modern Nīlgaḍh fort and the territorial division covers the whole of eastern part of Hōshangābād district upto Sohāgpūr.

Dēvanadī (line 42) - It can be identified with the river Dēnawa, which originates near Pachamarhi from Satapura hills and flows about 15 kms to the south of Sohāgpūr, near Madai in the reserve forest area.

Narmadāpura (line 51) - The Bhopal copper-plate of *mahākumāra* Udayavarman, dated Vikrama 1256 also mentions one Narmadāpura-*pratijakaranaka*.²² It is identified by J.F. Fleet with an ancient name of Hōshangābād, which is situated on the southern bank of Narmada and is a district headquarters in Madhya Pradesh.

Text

- 1 सिद्धं॥ॐनमःसर्वज्ञाय॥आनमाखिलवासवःशिववधूनेत्रोत्सवावैभवोभावाभावविभावभावविसदस्याद्वादवागी
श्वरः।नांस्तोव्यस्तसमस्त पापनिकरःचौकौ-
- 2 रवाधीश्वरःशान्त्यैशान्तिजिनेश्वरोस्तुविसदस्याद्वादवागीश्वरः॥श्रीनाभिपद्ममरुदुत्तमशक्तिशुक्तेरुद्भूतमूर्तिर
भवद्भूविकोपिदेवः।दृग्बोधवीर्यविभवोविभ-
- 3 वोनुभूतेर्भूयादसा च भवभावविधाम्सुदेवः॥ दीक्ष्याभिषेकजल सङ्कुलकेशपाशः पायात्सपावन
तपोवनमादध्यानः। हेमाद्रिशृङ्गसृतकेकिकुलोपमेय॥
- 4 नाभेय निर्दलितकल्मषमालुध्यातः॥ पीतांशपीठलुठितावृषभेश्वरस्य भास्वन्तमालदलकोमलनीलभासः।
प्राप्तास्तताः शुशुभिरसमरे जिगीषोःशङ्केत-
- 5 रांस्मररिपुंशरधीइवैताः॥ध्यानारणिप्रभव वह्निशिखाभिरुच्चैर्दग्धधकर्मविपिनेर्धविभासनाय। यजानभानु
रुदियाय ददानुदेवः सिद्धिप्रिया प्रियतमो
- 6 वृषभःश्रियम्बः॥ श्रीमान् जिह्नगमसागमसावभाणनिर्व्वाणकारणमसावताद्विचित्रम्। माम्मारवोपि
रमणीयतरोशरोभिः पिण्डद्रुमेण सुमनोभिरताद्वि-
- 7 चित्रम्॥ कैःकैर्नदेव तवपादयुगोपकण्ठेकुण्ठवसद्भिरवोधिसमाधिभावः। ब्रह्मस्वरूप
परतोस्तिनकिम्परम्पमौ पम्पगम्यमुपयाति नकोपिभावः॥ स्याद्वा-
- 8 दवादविदिताभवभावभावभावभावदलिताभवभावभावः।प्लाव्यान्मलम्बिमलसेननिरूपिभावः
सद्बोधदीपकलिताखिलविश्वभावः॥ विकाशसङ्कासवपु-
- 9 र्व्वहन्तीविकाशवतामरसञ्जषन्ती।दिगम्बराणाम्बदनारविन्दे वाग्देवतासम्बसतांसदैव॥*॥अथास्ति
वंशोत्रमहेश्वरादिपुराहवदेवालय मूर्द्वगामी।क्षौणीभृता-

- 10 स्पादतयधिस्टः प्रौढप्रभावो बहुपर्वशाली॥प्रोत्रुद्गताश्लिषितवातपधावकाशे वंशेमहाध्वजैवाम्बरबन्धुरश्रीः।
योन्नारुरोहगुणसन्ततिपूर्णमू-
- 11 तिर्न्नामाक साधुरभवच्छ शिशुभकीर्तिः॥
श्रीमज्जिनेन्द्रपदपद्मनतोच्चभालचूलामणिदयुमणिभासिशिरोवतंसः। गाङ्गेयकुम्भ निभसुन्दरधीवरांशः॥
- 12 श्री जैनशासनसरोवरराजहंसः॥ गामासमाहवस्य वणिग्वरस्य ज . प्रियासूहवनामधेया। रूपेणयस्यानलभेत
साम्यम्मृगोदृशः सास्मरराजजाया॥य-
- 13 स्याः कलेबरसरः सरसं रराज लावन्य नीर निकरं सदुरोज चक्रि। श्री कुन्तलालिलुलितालकसैवलंच
सददीर्घनेत्रषमानन पङ्कजश्री॥ तयोज्जिने-
- 14 न्द्राङ्गि सरोजभाजोः पद्माप्रियो जायतपद्मपुत्रः। दानामृतप्रीणित साधुपात्रः पुण्यप्रभाविष्कृत
शुद्धगोत्रः॥ सर्वज्ञदर्शनसमुन्नति दत्तचित्तोवित्तोपचार च-
- 15 तुरोन्वरमित्रबन्धुः। सौभाग्यभाग्यकलितोगुणरत्नसिन्धुः केनोपसीयततरामिहपद्मसाधुः॥ पद्मः पद्मायते
नित्यं सज्जनादित्य दर्शनात्। एतच्चित्रम्परंलोके-
- 16 यद्वन्ते कुमुदं सदा॥ नपङ्कजातो नजडाश्रयोपि हिमेनलुप्तोव च तीव्रमित्रः। सङ्कोचभावं नतनोतिरात्रौ
केनोपमीयेत सरोजकेन॥अपिच॥ यस्येदंहृदि-
- 17 सन्निविस्य कमलेसद्भूषणं दूषणं सपृष्टे शिशिरव्यपायिनि निशासङ्कोचिनि श्रीरियम्।पूर्णन्दोः
परिपूर्णदिग्भिरमलस्फारांशुभिर्यद्गुणाः स्पर्द्धन्तेप्रतिवासरं-
- 18 विजयताम्पद्मः सपद्मश्चिरम्॥ रेवापुरे सुरवरैर्विहितावतारे चैत्यालये प्रविपुले ससहस्रकूटे। यः
कारयेद्य जननदित देवराजो जैनत्रिकूटमुदम-
- 19 द्भुतपुण्यपुजः॥छ॥*॥ छ॥ अथ मातृपक्षे॥छ॥*॥ छ॥ ससोमतिः क्षितौजातः साधुः
साधुसमाश्रयः।गुणाःसः भुवोयस्यशोभन्ते स्यदयादयः॥ छ॥
- 20 कोकाभिधा प्रियाचास्य तत्सुताजनिमाहिनी॥ विभेवसाभवद्भानोः पद्मसद्मविकाशिनी॥ सीतेव रामस्य
सतीवशम्भोः सावित्रीकेवात्र पयोजयोनेः।
- 21 श्रीश्वेतभानोरिहरोहिणीवतङ्गेहिनी साजनिमाहिनीति॥ जिनेन्द्रपादाग्रनखोदयेन्दु सदंशुमालाप्लुतगात्रकश्रीः।
पूजाविधौ साशुमनोभिरामाचि-
- 22 रंविरेजेसुरसुन्दरीव॥स्ववंशपूर्वाचलबालभानुस्तात्यामभून्मददलनामसूनुः।विस्तीर्णवक्षोजितमेरुसानुर्दुराग्रप्र

ग्रहतासिधेनुः॥देवाधिदेव

- 23 पदपद्म नखेन्दुदीप्तिसदर्पणस्फुरितशुद्धदशाननश्रीः। मन्दोदरीकररुहांकितकक्षमूलः
श्रीकुम्भकर्णकरध्यौतविशुद्धभालः॥ श्रीचन्द्रहासकलिता-
- 24 धरकन्धरांशरामाकुल स्वकुलकेशरि राजहंसः। योत्रैकवक्त्रसुभगोपिदशास्पदेस्यः सीतापहारिचरितः
शुशुभेपिवैश्यः॥ गुरोः केशवसेनस्य
- 25 श्रीपादाम्बुजरेणुना। अकारि धूसरायेनकुन्तलालिरुपासनात्॥ अपिच॥ प्राभृतज्ञ मुनिकेशवसेनपादपद्म
मकरन्दसदालिः। जैनधर्मशालि-
- 26 लामलमौलिः पात्रलोकवदनार्पितशालिः॥श्रीसद्मपद्मतनुजो जिनधर्मभारप्रोद्धारकर्मणिसुरारिवराहलीलः।
मादधूकसाधुरजनीहनिरी-
- 27 ह पादपूजाप्रणामविहितांजलिभासिभालः॥काष्ठाद्गनास्तवतटेविकटेलुठन्तीकीर्तिः परत्र हित सदधृश
सम्बलस्य। मुक्तामयामलगुणास्फटिको-
- 28 पलाताहारावलीवकिलराजतिमद्दलस्य॥श्रीमद्दलस्यकमलाक्षिदिगन्तमूर्तिःकीर्तिर्निरन्तरमणीयतकेरलीभिः।शु
ण्वन्मृगोमृगमदावि॥
- 29 कक्षभालेवालेविलम्बयतिवाति मरुद्वसन्ते॥ ताम्बूलपत्रैः क्रमुकैर्विचित्रैर्वाग्देवतामर्चयतिस्म सोक्तः।
दयादिनेदान मिवाततानशक्नोतिवैव-
- 30 णिनुसस्यविक्रवः॥ पाधोधिपुत्रीव सुपर्णकेतोः कन्तोरतिश्चैवसचीवजिष्णाः। अर्द्धाङ्गलक्ष्मीरिति
मद्दलस्य प्रहेलिका जायत निधिनीति॥ विकाश
- 31 मानाकुमुदं समानासत्कीर्तिं शुभीकृतदिग्विताना। वसन्तमित्रस्यमुदेस्ततक्षीरेजेतरां साशरदीवचान्डी॥
रोलम्बमालानितनीलवाला सार्द्धेन्दुभा-
- 32 ला तवकेलिशाला। अतुल्य लावण्य पयोधिवेला मन्ददगतिद्वेपित हंसलीला॥
यस्यागतीराकृतिनातिनिर्जितो जगाम पाधो-
- 33 धीरितीव नीलतां। उरोजयुगमंप्रविलो . काननं कलाययुर्दूरतरं त्रपाकुलाः॥त्रिमागर्गयाकित्रिदिवापगेव
वीणारवां-
- 34 किं शुचिसारदेव। मुनीन्द्रसंघस्य चतुर्विधस्य सवत्सला शासनदेवतेच॥*॥*॥*॥ श्रीमालवे वहलशालि
जितान्य

- 35 देशोदेशोस्ति नीलगिरिनाम मनोभिरामः। सौभाग्ययोग्य रमणीरचितो॥ हारेसौभाग्य सुन्दरपुरे
सहकारसारे॥
- 36 यस्मिन्पुरे पौरवराङ्ग नानाङ्गाङ्गेय गौरीस्फुरदङ्गकान्तिः। श्रीमारवीरस्य विलाशवेस्म सञ्चार
दीपश्रियमातनोति॥
- 37 ॥ अथ ॥ श्रीविक्रमाकर्क स्वसुरङ्ग भवोबभूव श्रीहर्षदेव इति हर्षित चित्तवृतिः। षड्दर्शनेषुफलदो
भुविकल्पशाखी
- 38 शुभाभकीर्तिधवलीकृत दिग्विसन्तिः॥ पापान्तकन्तनुमताम्बिपदाम्प्रमाधम् प्रतिष्ठितप्रभुरिमञ्जित
शान्तिनाथम्। दे-
- 39 वायभानुनिगमान्प्रददौनरेन्द्रः श्रीनर्मदोदक पवित्रित दर्भ हस्तः॥ श्रीसीयक
प्रोत्पलराजराजश्रीसिन्धुराजात्मज-
- 40 भोजदेवभूपोदयादित्यनरादिवर्मयशः सुवर्माजयवर्मभूपैः॥ कुमारैः श्रीपरमारैरिभिर्मालवभूमिपैः। पालि-
- 41 ताः सन्त्य यामाद्वादशापि महान्मतिः॥ खुटामकनामा खेटकोनिषद्विकायाः खेटकख।
प्राव्यपाव्योर्ददिशोर्व्वत्ममर्यादा
- 42 प्रतिच्यांदिशिकोञ्चकविहारं लक्ष्मीकृत्योदीच्यांदिशि
देवनदीमर्यादीकृत्यैवञ्चनुराघाटविशुद्धापल्लिकावसतिसम्यु-
- 43 क्तभगवतोर्हतः शान्तिनाथस्य भूमिः॥ स्वदत्ताम्परदत्ताम्वायोहरन्तिवसुन्धराम्। महाहयोहि जायन्ते . .
काटरवा . -
- 44 नः॥ देशीगणेस्वर्णचंद्रोवीरचन्द्रस्ततोभवत्। पूर्णचन्द्रोधवालेन्दुर्नाम्नासूरिरजायत॥*॥अथ॥ रेवापुरात्समा-
- 45 गत्य साधुमादूः प्रियासखः। वासुवास्तव्यतामापनिः पापामलश्रीमुखः॥ श्रीसोमदेवोपरपघटश्च सलक्षणै ल-
- 46 क्षणतामुपेतः। आसन्नमीभूषित शुद्धगोत्राः पुत्रास्त्रयस्तामरसोद्भवस्य॥वपुर्व्वयःस्त्रीवसुमन्दिराणि
संभाव्यचित्ते
- 47 क्षणभंगुराणि। श्री सूत्रधारस्य जगाम वेश्म सशिलपिनां संघमिमंजुहाव॥ उददमुखमठस्यादौ
जीर्णोद्धारसचीकरन्।
- 48 तन्मठात्पूर्व्वदिग्भागे जिनागारमकारयन्॥ अपिच॥ प्रासादमेकं जिनबिम्बनिष्ठं मठसठं त्यज्यविरज्य
पापान्। श्रीमण्डपं शां-

- 49 तिजेनेश्वरस्य प्राचीकरत्पद्मशरीरजन्मा॥ महामठोद . दिग्देवकुलिकाकिलमददल। प्रोद्भीकृतेवतेकीर्त्या
नि
- 50 र्मलाङ्गुलिकाऽमल॥अम्बिकान्देवतांचैव रोहिणीं गुणरोहिणीं। सभद्रं माणिभद्रं च कारयामास सदगुणः॥
योत्रा-
- 51 दौ देवतानिष्ठां प्रतिष्ठां नर्मदापुरे। पितृकारित प्रसादत्रितयेकारयेदितः॥ श्रेष्ठां प्रतिष्ठां ध्वजारोपणं च
प्राची
- 52 करन्मददलसाधुरत्न। श्रीपद्मसाधोस्तनयस्य कीर्तिर्द्यान्दत्तपत्रेवहिवलातीव॥कृपन्नाभिगन्तीरां रितौ
पुण्यव
- 53 तींसतीम्। निम्धिनीवल्लभो रोपद्धधूटीमिव वाटिकाम्॥ सार्द्धेन्दुनितलेन श्रीमददलेन महात्मना।
प्रशस्तिकाद्वयं
- 54 द्वारिशान्तिरारोपिपावनम्॥श्रीमददलायतेस्वस्तिगतस्तिमिलन्मण्डले। येनारोप्यात्मनोनाम
प्रस्फुरत्चन्द्रमण्डले॥*
- 55 नरेन्द्रसे . द्भिसरोजभृङ्गः कृतीकृतज्ञो गुणरत्नधामा।
साहित्यविद्यामृतस्यन्दिगुर्योमुनीन्द्रचन्द्रोऽमलसेननामा॥ साधु-
- 56 र्यभा . . रसानुविद्वामृददुस्वरालापवतीस्वराज्याः। श्लेषैश्चितान्दुर्लभतामुपेतां
केलीमिवैतामकरोत्प्रशस्तिम्॥ सम्बत् १२४४॥*

Notes and References

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4. *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. I, pp. 226 ff.
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6. Gangully, D.C., 1933, *History of the Paramar Dynasty*, The University of Daccan, p. 47 and *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. 7, pt. 1, p. 13, fn. 4.
7. *Indian Antiquary*, Vol. XLII, p. 258.
8. *Ibid.*, Vol. X, pp. 158-62.
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11. Pratipal Bhatia, 1967, *The Paramāras*, Munishiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, p. 125. The Mālawā region again went into the hands of Chālukya of Gujarat, as Ballāla faced defeat in their hands.
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